

Disaster Preparedness and Management in Saudi Arabia: An Empirical Investigation

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Abstract : Disaster preparedness is a key success factor for any effective disaster management practices. This paper evaluates the disaster preparedness and management in Saudi Arabia using an empirical investigation approach. It presents the results of the survey conducted by interviewing representatives of the Saudi decision-makers and administrators responsible for disaster control in Jeddah before, during and after flooding in 2009 and 2010. First, demographics of the respondents are presented, followed by quantitative analysis of their views and experiences regarding the Kingdom's readiness before and after each flood. This is shown as a series of dependent and independent variables. Following this is a list of respondents' priorities for disaster preparation in the Kingdom.

Keywords : disaster response policy, crisis management, effective service delivery, Jeddah

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